

STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION IN RELATION TO TEACHER SELF EFFICACY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Teaching in the twenty-first century presents numerous obstacles for teachers, and as a result, they must take on more responsibilities in their schools in order to meet the expectations of students, parents, and school administration. In this context, the study looked at the association between teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction. The survey included 167 male and female instructors from government and private secondary schools in the Punjab state district of Amritsar. The data was collected using a non-random sampling technique. This study is classified as descriptive research design and the data was analysed using the descriptive statistics along with t-test, correlation, and anova. According to the findings, there is a strong and positive association between teacher self efficacy and job satisfaction.

Keywords: Teacher, Job Satisfaction, Teacher Self Efficacy

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INTRODUCTION: A developing country's educational system is commonly seen as its guiding principle. Education directly takes an active role in creating healthy societies. The education process that informally starts in the family is formally continued in schools. In schools, it is the teachers who carry out the task of raising community members and when individuals are desired to be trained, the motivational beliefs of the teachers who guide the teaching-learning process gain importance (Bandura, 1997). Effective teachers are essential for the accomplishment of an educational system.

The teachers play the most crucial and essential role in the development of the whole education system. . Laying the emphasis on teachers' qualities the report of Kothari Commission (1964-66) mentioned that "Of all the factors which determine the quality of education and its contribution to national development, the teacher is undoubtedly the most important. It is on his personal qualities and character, his educational qualifications and professional competence that the success of all educational endeavours must ultimately depend." The National Policy on Education(1986) placed immense trust in the teacher and his role in nation building. In the NPE, 1986 and its Revised Version 1992, it has been repeatedly remarked that 'No system of Education can rise above the level of its teachers.

There are many qualities, duties and responsibilities of a teacher for the development of society. There exists no society without students, men or teachers. In other sense educational development also means society development also. Teachers have to teach effectively and motivate the students in the field of education. No system of education, no syllabus methodology, no textbook and rise above the level of its teachers. If a country wants to have quality education it must have quality teachers.

Teaching in the twenty-first century also presents a variety of obstacles for educators. Because of these issues, instructors must take on greater responsibilities in their schools and fulfil the expectations of students, parents, and the community. These expectations created a demand for lifelong learning with competencies such as critical thinking, problem solving, teamwork, and the use of information and communication technologies, which has significantly altered teachers' roles. A high demanding educational system has made the teaching profession extremely challenging, as high-performance is expected from teachers. Teachers that are happy in their employment typically have a high level of professional competence and feel that they could manage, organize and perform specific tasks and behaviour, even in case of failure. The purpose of this study is to provide a relation between job satisfaction and self-efficacy.

JOB SATISFACTION: Job satisfaction has been a subject of research to help industries understand the needs of a large and diverse workforce. Hoppock first defined job satisfaction as a combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances causing employees to be satisfied professionally (Jiang, 2005). Job satisfaction is defined to be an overall belief about one's own job in terms of definite aspects of the occupation (work, pay promotion, co-workers job. he concept of job satisfaction is defined as the positive emotional

state of individuals about their job and job experience (Locke, 1976). Job satisfaction can be explained as the affective orientation of individuals towards their roles in the job they do, and their feelings and attitudes towards their jobs (Green, 2000; Turcan, 2011). Satisfaction with a job occurs when the gains and expectations of the individual are in harmony (Bingöl, 1990). When the concept of job satisfaction is examined, it can be stated that the factors that cause self-efficacy beliefs have similarity. Indeed, the sources that make up job satisfaction are addressed under the cognitive and affective dimensions (Scott & Judge, 1996).

Job satisfaction is defined to be an overall belief about one's own job in terms of definite aspects of the occupation (work, pay promotion). Job Satisfaction is a compounding of two words 'job' and 'satisfaction'. Job is an occupational activity performed by an individual in return for monetary reward (Venkateswaran, 2015), while satisfaction is a word which is hard to determine. The teacher, being a catalytic agent in the process of education, dispenses knowledge, forms time schedules, selects reading materials, plays the role of subject specialist and helps pupils to overcome their difficulties and provides learning support. Job satisfaction is an emotional relation to an employee's work status.

TEACHER SELF EFFICACY: Albert Bandura, a Canadian-American psychologist and professor at Stanford University, developed the self-efficacy theory in 1977.. He was the first one who introduced the concept before another psychologist such as Kathy Kolbe (2009) who also discussed the concept. Bandura (1977) defined self-efficacy as “a person’s particular set of beliefs that determine how well one can execute a plan of action in prospective situations” (Bandura, 1977). In view of Bandura’s self-competence theory, four sources of people’s efficacy beliefs had been developed. These four sources are deemed to be essential in developing the self-efficacy of teachers: a) Mastery learning experience, b) Vicarious experience, c) Social persuasion d) Physiological and emotional state.

Kolbe (2009) commented that self-efficacy is a determining factor in measuring cognitive strength, determination, and perseverance to overcome obstacles and achieve goals. It provides the foundation for motivation, well-being, and personal accomplishment (Lopez-Garrido, 2020) and it enables the person to handle stress, anxiety, adversities, and achieve performance (Lopez-Garrido, 2020). Self-efficacy is the belief of individuals in their capacity to produce behaviours appropriate to the events they encounter in their lives (Pajares, 2002; Zimmerman, 1990). Self-efficacy belief is a quality expected of teachers (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001).

Also, researchers observed teachers with low efficacy often spent more time on nonacademic learning activities, ignored students having learning difficulties, and criticised students for failures (Gibson & Dembo, 1984). Gibson and Dembo (1984) discovered that self-efficacy was an important factor in successful school improvement efforts. As research on teacher self-efficacy has continued to emerge, it has become an important concept in education. Coladarci (1992) examined teacher perceived instructional self-efficacy as a predictor of longevity and commitment to the profession of education. However, researchers have found self-efficacy to be an excellent predictor of teacher behaviours including, attendance, perseverance through difficult situations and job satisfaction.

Teachers are expected to love their professions, to have a positive attitude towards their jobs, to be satisfied with what their professions bring to them, and to have high self-efficacy beliefs that they can do their jobs. These teacher characteristics are effective in raising the members of society by gaining the desired characteristics and thus in establishing a society with the desired criteria (Buluç & Demir, 2015). At this point, studies examining the relationships between teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction gain importance. The positive impact of teacher self-efficacy on job satisfaction is widely supported in the literature (Arslan, 2019; Buluç & Demir, 2015; Demir, 2020; Klassen & Chiu, 2010; Saracaloğlu et al., 2017; Soto & Rojas, 2019)

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE :

Aftab, Dhahir and Khatoon (2016) conducted a Study entitled Determinants of Job Satisfaction among Secondary School Teachers in India. This study's goal was to provide empirical data on differences in secondary school teachers' job satisfaction in Uttar Pradesh (India) based on a set of independent variables (gender, qualification, teaching experience, salary, subjects taught, nature of job and marital status). The population consists of 281 male and 327 female teachers from 41 schools. The results of the analysis showed that gender had the greatest influence on teachers' job satisfaction. The analysis showed that gender had a great influence on the job satisfaction of the teachers. Moreover, the female teachers enjoyed more job satisfaction in their job than male teachers.

Türkoglu et al. (2017) analysed the relationship of self-efficacy to job satisfaction for a sample of teachers at the elementary, middle and high school levels. The sample consisted of 295 teachers with experience ranging from 1 to 29 years in a school district located in Istanbul. The results showed a strong correlation between job satisfaction and self-efficacy.

Mocheche, Bosire and Raburu (2018) conducted a study entitled Influence of Gender on Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Kenya. The study's goal was to look into the effect of gender on job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Kisii Central Sub-County, Kenya. A stratified sample of 306 students was drawn from all secondary school categories, followed by gender stratification. Female teachers had a slightly higher job satisfaction score of 51.52, with a standard deviation of 3.0 and a standard error of .240, compared to male teachers, who had a mean score of 50.29, with a standard deviation of 5.58 and a standard error of .544 in the level of job satisfaction.

Sharma (2018) conducted a study entitled A Study of Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers. The study's main goal was to compare job satisfaction among secondary school teachers based on gender and geography. A purposive sample of 200 male and female teachers was selected equally from 20 secondary schools of Pratapgarh district of Uttar Pradesh. The results revealed that teachers of government schools were more satisfied with their job than the teachers of private schools.

Pooja (2018) investigated the relationship between job satisfaction and occupational self-efficacy and the difference between the levels of job satisfaction and occupational self-efficacy among government and private school teachers. The sample included 60 teachers, three from public schools and thirty from private institutions. The association result suggests a significant relationship between job happiness and occupational self-efficacy. The findings also reveal a significant gender difference in job satisfaction and occupational self-efficacy.

Narasimha, M, L. & Reddy, L.K. (2019) examined the impact of emotional maturity, intelligence and self-efficacy on the academic achievement of teacher trainees. The study's sample included 400 teacher trainees drawn from various B.Ed. institutes in Andhra Pradesh's Kadapa district. The study's methods included the Emotional maturity scale, Raven's Progressive matrices, and the General self-efficacy scale (GSE). The mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used to examine the data. The results demonstrate that there is a considerable difference in emotional maturity, IQ, and self-efficacy between male and female trainees.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem was stated as under :

STUDY OF THE JOB SATISFACTION IN RELATION TO TEACHER'S SELF EFFICACY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE RELATED TERMS

The key terms employed in the study were operationally defined as below:

Job Satisfaction- Job Satisfaction describes how contented an individual is with his or her job. It has been defined as a pleasurable emotional state caused by a work evaluation. In this study the Job satisfaction is defined in terms of the scores of a Secondary school teacher's on Job satisfaction Scale constructed by Dr. Amar Singh and T.R. Sharma (1999)

Teacher Self-Efficacy- Self-efficacy is the extent to which one judges oneself able to do the tasks inherent in a given career or vocational pursuit. In this study the Self-efficacy is defined in terms of the scores of a Secondary school teacher's on Self-efficacy Scale constructed by Dr. Puneet Kaur and Sarabjit Kaur Ranu (2018).

OBJECTIVES :

1. To study job satisfaction of secondary school male and female teachers;
2. To study self efficacy in secondary school male and female teachers;
3. To study job satisfaction of government and private secondary school teachers;
4. To study self-efficacy of government and private secondary school teachers;
5. To study the relationship between job satisfaction and self efficacy of secondary school teachers.
6. To study the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers at different levels of self efficacy.

HYPOTHESES:

1. There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers;
2. There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of male and female secondary school teachers;
3. There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of government and private secondary school teachers;
4. There is no significant difference in the self efficacy of government and private secondary school teachers;
5. There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and self efficacy of secondary school teachers.
6. There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers at different levels of self efficacy.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design : Descriptive method of research was used for the study.

Research Tools : Following tools were used in the study

Job Satisfaction scale by Dr.Amar Singh and T.R. Sharma (1999)

Teacher Self-Efficacy scale by Puneet Kaur and Sarbjit Kaur Ranu (2018)

Sample and Selection Criteria : The population of the study included 167 Government and Private secondary school teachers selected through Non-Random sampling technique.

Statistical Analysis Techniques: Following statistical techniques have been used:

1. Mean and Standard Deviation of various sub groups was compared
2. t-test and correlation were employed to study the relationship between variables

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

DIFFERENCE IN THE JOB SATISFACTION OF MALE AND FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHER

Hypothesis-1 was framed to examine that **“There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of male and female secondary school teachers”**.

To test the hypothesis, the t-test was used to assess whether there was a significant difference in job satisfaction between male and female secondary school teachers. The results of this analysis are shown in the table

Table 1 Showing Mean, S.D. and t-value of Job Satisfaction among Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Gender	Mean	S.D	Std. Error mean	t-value	P - Value	Inference
Job-satisfaction	Male	74.742	11.8152	2.1221	5.083	0.000	Significant
	Female	64.925	8.6693	.8420			

The table clearly shows that the mean value of job satisfaction for male teachers is 74.742, while the mean value of job satisfaction for female teachers is 64.925, which is much lower than the job satisfaction for male teachers. Furthermore, the table shows that the calculated

p - value, 0.000, is smaller than the p - value at the 0.05 threshold of significance, indicating that there exists a significant difference between male and female teachers w.r.t their job satisfaction. Hence, the above stated null hypothesis is not accepted.

DIFFERENCE IN THE SELF-EFFICACY OF MALE AND FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Hypothesis-2 was framed to examine that “**There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of male and female secondary school teachers**”.

To test the hypothesis, the t-test was used to assess whether there was a significant difference in self-efficacy between male and female secondary school teachers. The results of this analysis are shown in the table

Table 2 Showing Mean, S.D. and t-value of Self Efficacy among Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Gender	Mean	S.D	Std. Error mean	t-value	P - Value	Inference
Self-Efficacy	Male	90.806	6.3057	1.1325	4.658	0.001	Significant
	Female	82.434	9.3961	.9126			

The table clearly shows that the mean value of male teachers' self-efficacy is 90.806 and the mean value of female teachers' self-efficacy is 82.434, which is less than the self-efficacy of male teachers. Furthermore, the table shows that the calculated p - value, 0.001, is smaller than the p - value at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there exists a significant difference between male and female teachers w.r.t their self- efficacy. Hence, the above stated null hypothesis is not accepted.

DIFFERENCE IN THE JOB SATISFACTION OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Hypothesis-3 was framed to examine that “**There is no significant difference in the Job Satisfaction of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers**”

To test the hypothesis, the t-test was used to assess whether there was a significant difference in job satisfaction between government and private secondary school teachers. The results of this analysis are shown in the table

Table 3 Showing Mean, S.D. and t-value of Job Satisfaction among Government and Private Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Type of school	Mean	S.D	Std. Error mean	t-value	P - Value	Inference
Job-satisfaction	Government	69.439	10.3895	2.1221	2.567(equal variances assumed)	0.011	Significant
	Private	65.014	8.6693	9.7870			

The table clearly shows that the mean value of job satisfaction for government school instructors is 69.439, whereas the mean value of job satisfaction for private teachers is 65.014, which is lower than the mean value of job satisfaction for government school teachers. Furthermore, the table shows that the calculated p - value, 0.011, is smaller than the p - value at the 0.05 threshold of significance, indicating that there exists a significant difference between government school teachers and private school teachers w.r.t their job satisfaction. Hence, the above stated null hypothesis is not accepted.

DIFFERENCE IN THE SELF-EFFICACY OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Hypothesis-4 was framed to examine that “**There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of government and private secondary school teachers**”

To test the hypothesis, t-test was applied to determine the significant difference in the self efficacy of government and private secondary school teachers. The result of this analysis has been reported in the table

Table 4 Showing Mean, S.D. and t-value of Self Efficacy Among Government And Private Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Type of school	Mean	S.D	Std. Error mean	t-value	P - Value	Inference
Self-Efficacy	Government	85.470	9.9819	1.2287	1.367	0.004	Not Significant
	Private	83.268	8.8656	1.0522			

The table clearly shows that the mean value of self- efficacy of government school instructors is 85.470, whereas the mean value of self- efficacy of private school teachers is 83.268, which is smaller than the mean value of self- efficacy of government school teachers. Furthermore, the table shows that the calculated p - value, 0.004, is smaller than the p - value at the 0.05 threshold of significance, indicating that there exists a significant difference between government and private school teachers w.r.t their self- efficacy. Hence, the above stated null hypothesis is not accepted.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND SELF-EFFICACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Hypothesis-5 was framed to examine that “**There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and self-efficacy of secondary school teachers**”. Correlation was used to examine the hypothesis of the association between self efficacy and job satisfaction of government school teachers. The outcome is shown in the table

Table 5 Showing correlations between Job Satisfaction and Self Efficacy of Secondary School Teachers

		TEACHER	SELF
		EFFICACY SCALE	
JOB SATISFACTION SCALE		Pearson Correlation	.746**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	167

According to the table, the correlation value between job satisfaction and self efficacy is 0.746, and the P value is 0.000. The findings suggest that teachers' self-efficacy is strongly and positively connected to their job satisfaction. Hence, the hypothesis "There is no significant relationship between the job satisfaction and self efficacy of secondary school teachers" has not been accepted.

DIFFERENCE IN THE JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT LEVELS OF SELF-EFFICACY

Hypothesis-6 was framed to examine that "There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers with respect to different levels of teacher self-efficacy.

To test this hypothesis one way ANOVA was applied to test the relationship between the Job Satisfaction of secondary school teachers with respect to different levels of Self Efficacy.

TABLE 6 Showing values Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers with respect to different levels of Self Efficacy

	Levels of Self Efficacy	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		F	Sig.
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Job Satisfaction	EXTREMELY HIGH SELF EFFICACY	37	78.030	10.4238	1.8145	74.334	81.726	30.664	0.48
	HIGH SELF EFFICACY	66	68.107	5.3315	.7124	66.679	69.535		
	NEUTRAL	34	60.458	6.7372	1.3752	57.613	63.303		
	LOW EFFICACY	19	57.933	5.9338	1.5321	54.647	61.219		
	EXTREMELY LOW SELF EFFICACY	11	54.286	2.7516	1.0400	51.741	56.831		
	Total	167	67.146	10.2867	.8789	65.408	68.884		

According to the above table, the F value for secondary school teachers' job satisfaction between groups is 30.664, and the P value is 0.048, which is greater than the P value at the 0.05 threshold of significance. Hence the above stated hypothesis "There is no significant difference in the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers with respect to different levels of self-efficacy" is not accepted.

CONCLUSION: The analysis revealed that the male and female teachers are found to be significantly different on the scores of Job Satisfaction and Self Efficacy. It also indicated a substantial difference in job satisfaction and self efficacy levels between government and private school instructors. The government secondary school teachers found to be more satisfied with their job than private school teachers. Male secondary school teachers are shown to be more satisfied with their jobs based on job satisfaction t-test results. Secondary school teachers that have a high sense of self-efficacy are reported to be the most content with their jobs.

Educational Implications of the Study

The following are the educational implications of the present study:

1. Job satisfaction and self-efficacy of the teachers are the vitally important aspects of the teaching profession. They play a significant role in affecting the work performance of the teachers. It is essential to study them thoroughly and deeply in order to plan a strategy for helping the teachers as well as the entire teaching learning process.
2. For maintaining the quality and competency of any educational institution, concerned authorities must be impartial in recruiting the quality faculties. They may select only those individuals who show satisfaction with the teaching job. They must also possess a higher level of self-efficacy.
3. Because the role of teacher is of great importance in creating a building into an educational institution, it is advised to determine the eligible candidates' attitude towards teaching profession and self-efficacy before their recruitment in the teaching profession.
4. Job satisfaction is positively correlated with self-efficacy. Hence, efforts should be made to enhance teachers' job satisfaction through various career promotion schemes. They should be provided with a conducive organisational climate, should be free to develop friendly relations among teachers & students, among teachers & teachers and teachers & management.

5. In-service teacher training programs should be designed in such a way that it would provide adequate opportunities for teachers to develop competency to face the various real teaching life situations. It would likewise raise the positive working attitude of teachers and make them self-sufficient.

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